

Expansion of English Education in India

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Abstract

The topic is about the impact of English Education in India in Pre-independence and Post independence era. It provides the glimpse of the colonial impact of education system on Indian pedagogy, which reflect the occidental philosophy and concepts on the oriental world, which finally leads to the drastic change in the national education system and national feeling of our own educational pattern and national pride of Indian philosophy merges in new education policy.

Keyword: Pre-independence, Expansion, Hindi-region, English Education.

INTRODUCTION

1. THE EXPANSION AND EVOLUTION OF ENGLISH EDUCATION IN HINDI-REGION

English language entered Hindi-region along with the establishment of English rule. English education, English literature, English thought and English civilization also entered here alongwith English language. Here it is necessary to know how did English education, language, literature, civilization, culture, thought and words enter Hindi-region.

2. THE COMMENCEMENT OF ENGLISH EDUCATION

The English people wanted to publicize and spread their English education and wanted to establish English as an official language. Hence, they regarded that the knowledge of English is essential for a high order of education while the vernacular languages must be employed to teach the far larger classes who are ignorant

of or imperfectly acquainted with English. In their own words, "We look, therefore, to English language and vernacular of India together as the media for the diffusion of European knowledge. Hence, by the effort of Lord Macaulay, English language was declared as an official language of India. Lord Macaulay was appointed as a member of law and a Chairman of general committee of education.

In 1828 A.D. Lord William Bentinck came to India as a Governor-General. He wanted to cultivate English alone. In support of his thinking, the views of B.D. Basu may be presented:

"It is the opinion of the Governor-General that all funds which are available for the purpose of education should be applied to the cultivation of English alone."

Before the special order of 1835, several schools were established at the following places:

3. THE EXPANSION OF ENGLISH EDUCATION

From 1825 A.D. to 1837A.D., eight schools were established at various places. English Literature was published by Agra Book Society established in 1837 A.D.

In 1843 A.D. High Schools were established at Allahabad, Meerut and Bareilly. First Engineering College was established at Roorkee in 1847^s A.D. In 1854, Eight Schools were established in Bareilly, Shahjahanpur, Agra, Mathura, Mainpuri, Aligarh, Ferrukhabad and Etawa. In 1857 A.D., three universities were established in Calcutta, Madras and Bombay. The colleges of Banaras, Agra and Bareilly were affiliated to Calcutta University.

After it, Schools were established in Lucknow, Allahabad and Aligarh which were changed into Universities with the passage of time :Canning College, Lucknow in 1864 A.D. Mysore Central College, Allahabad in 1872 A.D.

Mohammedan Anglo Oriental College, Aligarh in 1875 A.D. The examinees in Hindi-Region in different years were as follows:

Examination	1880-81	1890-91	1900-01	1903-04
Matriculation	297		606	810
Intermediate	48		204	197
Ordinary Bachelor Degree	24		105	167
				223

Higher Special Degree 7 11 29 24

The first University of Hindi-Region was established in Allahabad in 1887 A.D. and all colleges of this region were affiliated to this University. According to the census of 1901, English-speakers in Agra were

3,191.⁶At this time, there were 28 colleges¹ in Hindi-Region, which may be divided into the following three parts:

4. GOVERNMENTAL GOVT. AIDED PUBLIC

Allahabad	Lucknow	Agra St. Jones College
Banaras	Agra	Lucknow Christian College
	Aligarh Bareilly Gorakhpur Kanpur Meerut	Banaras Hindu College

After it, English Education went on evolving day-by-day. The Universities were established in Allahabad, Banaras, Lucknow, Aligarh, Agra, Patna, Bihar, Sagar, Jabalpur, Vikram, Delhi, Rajasthan, Gorakhpur, Roorkee,

Boards of Secondary Education also were established in Bihar, U.P., M.P., Rajasthan, Delhi| Ajmer, etc. On the basis of the Census of 1951, English speakers were.

Region	Population	English Speaker
U.P.	6,32,15,742	5,18,326
Bihar	4,02,25,947	2,63,625
M.P.	2,12,47,533	1,41,185
Punjab	1,26,41,205	3,24,815
Rajasthan	1,52,90,797	68,311
Delhi	17,44,072	1,62,678
H.P.	11,09,466	6,776
Total	15,54,74,762	14,85,756
		Less-than 1%

Since 1951, several Schools, Academies, Colleges and Universities have been established in Hindi-Region. Hence, English is going on developing now by leaps and bounds. And now-a-days English is a part and parcel of Hindi-Region.

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